

“I wanted to make a difference. I want to have an impact on the world and I want the world to be a better place.”

According to Sutherland, when he started his career in conservation, he realised that many libraries around the world weren't well stocked. As a result, many academics and community groups in the Global South in particular didn't have access to the latest research and thinking. So instead of receiving royalties from his early books, the money was spent on sending out free copies to people who would benefit from his work.

Digitisation opened up new possibilities. Research could be made available to people around the globe at the click of a button, paving the way for open access publishing.

But, access is still restricted – many academics have to pay for books or to get past paywalls.

Sutherland said: “Books are only accessible to a limited number of people and where there's the greatest need for conservation, these books are hardest to acquire and hardest to afford.”

William Sutherland,
Professor of Conservation
Biology and Director of
Research at the University
of Cambridge

Sutherland thinks open access publishing helps academics make a difference

Research has greater reach

Readers can access the latest research, insights and evidence

Geographical barriers are removed

Financial barriers are removed

There is greater equity of access